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New District Heating and Cooling Network at University of Cordoba in Spain – EU-funded project WEDISTRICT

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1. Introduction

The buildings sector represents the largest energy consumption sector in the European Union (EU-27), with residential buildings' accounting for 26% and commercial buildings accounting for 14% of the EU-27's final energy consumption [1]. Space heating accounted for 64% of the energy consumption in the residential sector with a renewables share of 27% of the space heating demand [2]. Achieving the European targets on climate neutrality until 2050, which were set in the European Green Deal [3], requires significant changes in the current buildings' heat supply and demand structures. Energy Efficiency First Principle (E1st) should assist governments and local authorities in achieving these targets in a cost-optimal mix of demand and supply-side resources and measures. E1st principle as defined in the Governance Regulation 2018/1999 [4] requires that alternative cost-efficient energy efficiency measures for both demand and supply side should be included in both, energy planning activities as well as in policy and investment decisions.

The 2021 published guidelines by the European Commission on bringing the E1st from principle to practice encourages policy makers to clearly define the role of district heating networks in reaching wider energy system objectives by including industrial excess heat, demand-side management, market access rules, etc. [5]. District heating and cooling (DHC) networks, and in particular 4th generation DHC (4GDH), are widely recognized as an important element in the future smart and sustainable energy system [6-8]. The 4GDH as a concept of smart thermal grids assists the development of the sustainable energy system by integrating large shares of renewable electricity generation. The 4GDH networks are characterized by lower supply temperatures, low energy demands and heat densities, and optimum interaction between energy sources, distribution networks and heat consumers [9]. This future system is able to balance fluctuating renewable energy sources (RES), electricity generation with power-to-heat (P2H) solutions and integrates large volumes of the available industrial excess heat [10-12]. Although the design, operation, and regulation of DHC systems are determined by national and municipal legislation, EU legislation such as the Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) [13] and the Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) [14] have the goal to enhance the usage of efficient DHC systems with respect to the E1st principle.

One of the requirements of Article 14 of the EED 2012/27/EU [13], its amendment 2018/2002/EU [15] and revised Annex VIII 2019/826/EU [16], is for Member States (MS) to carry out comprehensive assessments of the potentials for efficient DHC systems to supply the current and future heat demand. Part of the assessment includes a cost-benefit analysis to identify the most resource- and cost-efficient solutions for supplying heating and cooling demands from a societal perspective. The recast of the RED II 2018/2001/EU [14] requires the opening of DHC networks for third party RES or waste heat generators and thus improving supply-side efficiency.

On the other hand, the trends and future forecasts of the heating and cooling demands are largely influenced by the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2010/31/EU [17] and are mostly exogenously considered in the cost-benefit analysis of the efficient heating and cooling supply. According to Article 2a of the revised EPBD 2018/844/EU [18], each MS should establish a long-term renovation strategy (LTRS) to support the renovation of the national residential and non-residential building stock. Some of the requirements of the LTRS are to provide an overview of the national building stock, the identification of cost-effective approaches to renovation, and policies and actions to stimulate cost-effective deep renovation.

In the frame of the H2020 Wedistrict UE project a demonstrative renewable DHC installation is projected in the Campus of Rabanales at the University of Cordoba. This paper describes the basic characteristics and operational modes of this new DHC installation.

2. Renewable technologies and conceptual design

The demonstrative renewable DHC installation will cover the heating and cooling demand of Da Vinci I, II and III buildings and the heating demand of the Monte Cronos Sports Stadium at the Campus of Rabanales at the University of Cordoba. Seven new technologies will be integrated in this installation, see Table 1, as a combination of three different solar technologies, two biomass boilers, two absorption chillers and a Renewable Air-Cooling Unit (RACU). An Advanced Digitalization platform will control this network. RACU consists of a combination of desiccant wheel and indirect evaporative cooler. Wessun technology uses tracking concentrator for fixed tilt solar thermal collectors. A thermal power of 1.5 MW_{th} in heat generation and 0.47 MW_{th} in cooling generation is expected in this renewable DHC installation using the technologies described in Table 1.

Table 1. Renewable technologies used in DHC demo at University of Cordoba.

Technology	Thermal power [kW _{th}]	Other characteristics
Solar CSP	184	Net collecting area: 328 m ²
Solar Fresnel	240	Net collecting area: 445 m ²
Solar Wessun	85	Net collecting area: 137 m ²
Biomass boiler	995	Wood chips + Improved air filters
Conventional absorption chiller	413	Coefficient of performance: 0.75
Advanced absorption chiller	40	Coefficient of performance: 1.02
RACU	18	Coefficient of performance: 6.0
Advanced digitalization platform	-	Control and monitoring of the entire DHC network

The conceptual design of this renewable DHC installation is shown in Fig. 1. Renewable energy production is a block composed by three solar technologies and two biomass boilers. A 50 m³ sensible thermal storage tank is used to balance the energy production and the energy demand of the installation. In addition, a 10 m³ sensible thermal storage tank is used for the biomass boilers. A general collector is used to effectively distribute the energy production and the energy demand to the DHC net as well as the energy demand from the absorption chillers. The DHC network connects the general collector of technical plant to the substations located in Da Vinci Buildings and Monte Cronos Stadium. DHC network consists of buried insulated pipes with operating temperatures 95°C/70°C. Thermal substations in each building are connected to the existing heat pump collectors that distributes hot and cold water inside the buildings.

Fig. 1. Conceptual renewable DHC installation at University of Cordoba.

As a part of the WEDISTRIC project, an Advanced Digitalization Platform (ADP) will be developed and integrated. This platform will have the ability to aggregate, monitor, and control the operations of this DHC network to provide heating and cooling at University of Cordoba, exclusively powered by 100% renewable energy sources. The platform design will guarantee interoperability, high availability, scalability, and immediate reaction to disasters. In addition, a link will be established between the WEDISTRIC ADP and the Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) system of the new DHC network at the University of Cordoba.

3. Operational modes

Different operational modes will be implemented in this new DHC network at the University of Cordoba. Five basic operation modes in heat mode and five operation modes in cool mode are defined, as shown in Table 2. The selection of one mode of operation or another will be made based on the weather forecast and biomass resources in order to get optimal operational costs at each period of time. The basic operational modes are:

- Operational mode 1H. In this mode, the three solar technologies generate thermal energy to charge the thermal storage tank. If there is solar availability, the hydraulic circuits of the three solar collectors, CSP, Fresnel and Wessun, will be activated. It will be possible to prioritize and balance thermal production between the three solar technologies.
- Operational mode 2H. In this mode the discharge of the thermal energy storage tank will be used to cover energy demand of the buildings if there is thermal accumulation. The hydraulic circuit from this tank to the general collector of the DHC net will be activated.
- Operational mode 3H. Based on the operation of biomass boilers alone. A biomass boiler or both biomass boilers will be activated if there is no solar availability or no thermal accumulation to cover the energy demand.
- Operational mode 4H. Based on the combination of thermal production from solar technologies and biomass boilers. It will analyze which solar technologies have priority in this mode of operation. The percentage of operation of biomass boilers for this mode of operation will also be adjusted.
- Operational mode 1C. Similar to operational mode 1H, including operation of one absorption chiller or both absorption chillers and RACU to cover the cooling demand of the Da Vinci Building.
- Operational mode 2C. Similar to operational mode 2H, including operation of one absorption chiller or both absorption chillers and RACU to cover the cooling demand of the Da Vinci Building.
- Operational mode 3C. Similar to operational mode 3H, including operation of one absorption chiller or both absorption chillers and RACU to cover the cooling demand of the Da Vinci Building.
- Operational mode 4C. Similar to operational mode 4H, including operation of one absorption chiller or both absorption chillers and RACU to cover the cooling demand of the Da Vinci Building.

Table 2. Basic operational modes in the renewable DHC installation.

Operational mode		Description
Heat	1H	Thermal storage mode
	2H	Discharge thermal storage
	3H	Only biomass boilers
	4H	Solar and biomass boilers
Cool	1C	Thermal storage mode and absorption chillers and RACU
	2C	Discharge thermal storage and absorption chillers and RACU
	3C	Only biomass boilers and absorption chillers and RACU
	4C	Solar and biomass boilers and absorption chillers and RACU

In each of these modes, several Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be evaluated. As an example, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) [17] establishes a definition of the Renewable Energy Ratio, RER, for buildings in ISO 52000 [19]. Also, an auxiliary energy ratio, r_{aux} is defined for this DHC net as follows:

$$RER = \frac{E_{Pren}}{E_{Ptot}} \quad (1)$$

$$r_{aux} = \frac{\sum E_{aux}}{|Q_{del}|} \quad (2)$$

where:

- E_{Pren} : renewable primary energy used by the DHC network at University of Cordoba.
- E_{Ptot} : total primary energy used by the DHC network at University of Cordoba.
- $\sum E_{aux}$: auxiliary electrical energy use [kWh_{el}].
- Q_{del} : delivered thermal energy [kWh_{th}].

Other Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as non-renewable primary energy factor, equivalent CO₂ emission coefficient, local air pollutants emission coefficients, capital expenditures (CAPEX), operational expenditures (OPEX), levelized cost of energy (LCoE) and environmental social cost (sc), will be evaluated within this project.

4. Conclusions

A new Renewable District Heating and Cooling Network is projected to cover the heating and cooling demand of different buildings at the Campus of Rabanales of the University of Cordoba. The installation combines three different solar technologies, two biomass boilers, two absorption chillers and one Renewable Air-Cooling Unit. An Advanced Digitalization platform will control and monitor this DHC network. Based on this it can be concluded that:

- The main objective of the WEDISTRICT project is to demonstrate innovative 100% fossil free heating and cooling solutions for new and existing district heating and cooling systems.
- This DHC living lab at University of Cordoba will integrate, operate, and test a combination of renewable technologies in DHC networks as a way of decarbonizing heating and cooling of buildings.

This demo site in Spain could add complementary results to those obtained in other DHC demo installation within the Wedistrict project in Bucharest (Romania) and Lulea (Sweden).

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